

20 21

INTERNAL
**ANNUAL
REPORT**

Let's make life better

A NEW HOPE

Government are coming for you, endometriosis

France

In early January 2022, the French President, Emmanuel Macron, launched the first Action Plan to Fight Endometriosis. [Source](#) (Youtube)

Which country will follow?

Scotland

In August 2021, Scotland was bidding to become a 'world leader' in addressing women's health inequalities. A new plan included recommendations for better endometriosis diagnosis and treatment, and specialist menopause services. It also calls for a drive to create greater awareness of heart disease symptoms and risks.

Women's Health Minister Maree Todd said the strategy would drive wider change across health and social care services. She added that when women and girls are supported to lead healthy lives and fulfil their potential, the whole of society benefits. [Source](#)

Hungary

In the summer of 2021, the Hungarian Health Ministry announced that it would like to shorten the 4.5 years between the onset of symptoms and the final diagnosis of endometriosis even further.

Australia

In December 2017 in Australia, the Turnbull Government announced the development of the National Action Plan. This was the first National Action Plan for Endometriosis. It provided a platform for improving the awareness, understanding, treatment of, and research into, endometriosis and associated chronic pelvic pain in Australia. [Source](#) (PDF)

FEMaLe 2021 TIMELINE

What got done

1 January

FEMaLe Project begins

28 January

Press release about FEMaLe in Denmark

[Read it here \(English\)](#)

12 February

Online Kick-Off Meeting & General Assembly

March (Endometriosis Awareness Month)

Endomarch campaign in Hungary

- Interview in one of Budapest's radio channels
- Yellow tulips to patients on International Women's Day
- Live talk on Glamour's instagram profile

Social media campaign:

- Lost days

March 18

Executive Board meeting

25 March

Facebook Live Event: Meet the Experts

With Endometriose Foreningen in Denmark

March 27

Virtual event

With endometriosis experts in Hungary

FEMaLe 2021 TIMELINE

What got done

27 April

Executive Board meeting

28 May

Executive Board meeting

10-19 June

Balaton bike derby, public fundraising

12 June

Richter Health Town appearance
Kaposvár, Kossuth square

22 June

Work Package Leader meeting

26 June

Richter Health Town appearance
Miskolc, Szent István square

27 June

Richter Health Town appearance
Kiskunhalas, Bethlen square

FEMaLe 2021 TIMELINE

What got done

July ...●

Hungarian Health Ministry announcement

“ In accordance with the instructions of Minister Prof. Dr. Miklós Kásler, the Ministry is handling issues, such as infertility, the process of artificial insemination, and the diagnosis and treatment of endometriosis in a complex manner.

The Ministry is working with professional boards and committees to ensure that, in the long term, it has the human resources and modern equipment with international experience to improve the quality of life of tens of thousands of women.

It takes 4.5 years between the onset of symptoms and the final diagnosis in Hungary. We would like to shorten that four and a half year waiting time even further, so that people can receive the right care as soon as possible. With the introduction of the health service legal status, there is a clear separation between private and public healthcare.

“ We would like to stress that patients covered by social insurance who use public care must in all cases be treated free of charge by public institutions. Within the public care system, any institution may be chosen and the competent regional institution may not refuse patients who apply to it.

●..... 1-31 July

Virtual running

The ‘Easier together’ Foundation for Women’s Health organized a charity run between 1 and 31 July.

With running, our purpose was to raise the attention of as many people as possible to the disease, to spread knowledge about endometriosis and at the same time to raise donations, which we can later spend on related education.

VIRTUAL RUNNING
1-31 July 2021
FOR WOMEN AFFECTED BY ENDOMETRIOSIS

Distances: 1 km, 3 km, 5 km, 10 km, 20 km, 40 km | Entry fee: HUF 3,500
More info: www.endometriosismagyarorszag.hu

Facebook, Instagram, Twitter icons | [endometriosismagyarorszag](https://www.facebook.com/endometriosismagyarorszag)

endometriosis | MPFSZ

For the health of females - Together for women

For the health of females - Together for women

endometriosis
Magyarorszag

FEMaLe 2021 TIMELINE

What got done

August

Instagram advertisement

Instagram advertisements started in August to promote Lucy application and the FEMaLe project.

 endometriozismagyarorszag

24 August

Executive Board meeting

- LinkedIn: +37,000 views.
- Twitter: +29,000 impressions.

27 August

ENDORSE Foundational Meeting
Foundation of the Danish Endometriosis Research Group (ENDORSE)

1 September

Lucy application available on both Android & iOS

[Get the app here](#)

4 September

Richter Health Town appearance
Pécs, Kossuth square

7 September

Work Package Leader meeting

FEMaLe 2021 TIMELINE

What got done

11 September

Richter Health Town appearance
Dorog, Otthon square

18 September

Richter Health Town appearance
Budapest District IX, Albert Flórián street

23 September - 14 October

Libresse Pain dictionary and the Pain Museum
Every Spar and Interspar stores takes part in the promotion

2 October

'Endometriose Foreningen' annual meeting
Aarhus University Hospital, Denmark

5 October

Executive Board meeting
• LinkedIn: +45,000 views
• Twitter: +41,000 impressions

The first version of the Correlate platform was presented

9 October

Richter Health Town appearance
Szolnok, Kossuth square

FEMaLe 2021 TIMELINE

What got done

21 October

Menstruation in the Media Conference

In collaboration with the Menstruation Research Network at the University of Sheffield, FEMaLe focused on media narratives about menstruation.

2-3 November

FEMaLe Correlate event

9 November

Work Package Leader meeting

7 December

Executive Board meeting

- LinkedIn: +62,000 views
- Twitter: +70,000 impressions
- Instagram: 4,000+ exposures

Nine confirmed Advisory Board members

23 December

First FEMaLe animated video explainer

[Watch it here](#)

15 December

EEL Special Webinar

In collaboration with the European Endometriosis League, FEMaLe co-hosted the EEL Special Webinar on Machine Learning and Augmented Reality in the diagnosis of Endometriosis.

[\(Re\) watch the webinar here!](#)

WORK PACKAGE SUMMARY

page 1 of 2

WP1

We got started with the Half Double Methodology and it has been a positive addition to the FEMaLe Project.

WP2

We have implemented WP2 in the other work packages. Our ambition is to run workshops or webinars every second month. We are also working on how we can bring citizen science to the FEMaLe Project.

WP3

We have developed a study at reaching consensus on relevant symptoms and a questionnaire aimed at estimating the prevalence and geographical distribution of endometriosis symptoms. We will create a prediction model for endometriosis based on symptoms and other characteristics.

WP4

We have included Aalborg University in the project, and we are in the process of developing an analysis plan for moving forward.

WP5

The Lucy app has been released, translated and its software architecture restructured. Further we have been developing the Lucy Questionnaire, and the collected data from the app will be analyzed using artificial intelligence.

WORK PACKAGE SUMMARY

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WP6

We have started to collect video data and gained access to SurgAR sample segmentation tools. We are trying to adopt a semi-supervised image segmentation algorithm from other projects, which will make the segmentation in our project much easier and faster.

WP7

We are in the process of collecting videos with metadata. Further, we have started the annotation and training for surgeon labellers.

WP8

We have finished three out of ten mindfulness modules for MY-ENDO. The FEMaLe project and the MY-ENDO results have been presented at the Danish Endometriosis Patients Associations' Yearly Meeting, and we find that this has implications for both the patient organization and the patients with endometriosis.

WP9

We have utilized the social media accounts to communicate about the project and have started to interacting with our community consistently. In summary, we have engaged with more than 160.000 users across the platforms.

WP10

We held Executive Board meetings in February, March, April, May, August, October and December, and we conducted Work Package Leader meetings in June, September and November. We established fixed rhythms, which help the FEMaLers to collaborate across the ten work packages.

ALL 2021 WORK PACKAGES PRESENTATIONS

June

September

November

[Link to YouTube playlist](#)

[Link to YouTube playlist](#)

[Link to YouTube playlist](#)

[Link to all PP Slides](#)

[Link to all PP Slides](#)

[Link to all PP Slides](#)

FEMaLe COMMs KPIs

Performance on Social Media

2021 in numbers

210 POSTS
160,154 REACHED
763 AVG. REACH / POST
5,501 REACTIONS
26 AVG. REACTIONS / POST

LINKEDIN

145 FOLLOWERS
64 POSTS
1,512 REACTIONS
24 AVG. REACTIONS / POST
68,923 VIEWS
1,077 AVG. VIEWS / POST

TWITTER

870 FOLLOWERS
116 POSTS
3,516 REACTIONS
30 AVG. REACTIONS / POST
86,089 IMPRESSIONS
742 AVG. IMPRESSIONS / POST

INSTAGRAM

213 FOLLOWERS
30 POSTS
473 REACTIONS
16 AVG. REACTIONS / POST
5,142 EXPOSURES
171 AVG. EXPOSURES / POST

CONTEXT:

The above numbers are from August-December, starting from scratch on all platforms.

WP1

In more detail

We have got started with the Half Double Methodology. FEMaLers have attended a HDM course and have been certified. We have been facilitating 11 workshops and created 10 impact cases for each WP.

We have also held interviews with WP leaders to make an evaluation in collaboration with the Half Double Institute, affiliated to Aarhus University. The Baseline pulse check was very positive with an average score around 4 out of 5.

Overall Impact – KPI/measure

What were the KPIs?

- To create 11 Half Double and Impact Case workshops
- To create 10 Impact cases

Were the targets met?

Yes, we conducted 11 Impact Case workshops and created 10 Impact Cases.

WP2

In more detail

We have been drawing up an action plan to introduce new instruments and implement WP2 in the other work packages, and we proposed a framework for implementation to task leaders.

The ambition is to run a workshop or co-host a webinar every second month to share experiences about what has been developed and created. We are developing ideas with a university in Hungary on how we can bring citizen science to our activities in FEMaLe.

This will hopefully engage more young researchers to the field, with the ideas of creating a balance between genders.

Overall Impact – KPI/measure

What were the KPIs?

1. To identify 10 advisers and professionals in ethics, gender inclusion, RRI and open science.
2. To invite 10 advisers and professionals in ethics, gender inclusion, RRI and open science.
3. To identify 10 good practices and advisers for gender inclusion, RRI and open science.
4. To create an action plan for responsible innovation and research (including gender equity, inclusion, open sciences etc.)

Were the targets met?

We have partially reached the intended targets. This means that we will continue with the tasks that did not reach the intended targets in the WP2 Impact Case in Q1+Q2 2022 and additionally set new targets for 2022 Q1 and Q2. This has no critical consequences, as the next deliverables are due much later in the FEMaLe project.

WP3

In more detail

We have developed a study at reaching consensus on relevant symptoms to include in a survey for pre-menopausal women. Invitation material and questionnaire has been developed and translated into Hungarian, Danish, Turkish, French, and English. Local coordinators have agreed to help with the recruitment of patients and healthcare professionals.

In the United Kingdom we will create a prediction model for endometriosis based on symptoms and other characteristics looking at all women who have symptoms of endometriosis. The data will be used to make a prediction model combined with demographic data, which hopefully can be used in the future to determine if patients have endometriosis or not.

In Denmark we will estimate the prevalence and geographical distribution of endometriosis symptoms by using linkage between self-reported data and existing registry information. Also a PhD research fellow has been appointed to work on the project.

Overall Impact – KPI/measure

What were the KPIs?

1. To obtain ethical and data approvals.
2. To employ 4 dedicated staffs.
3. To disseminate online and offline in the UK.
4. To produce an action plan for launching the large-scale questionnaire.

Were the targets met?

We have partially reached the intended targets. This means that we will continue with the tasks that did not reach the intended targets in the WP3 Impact Case in Q1+Q2 2022 and additionally set new targets for 2022 Q1 and Q2.

WP4

In more detail

We have been working on including Aalborg University as a new Beneficiary in the project and they were unanimously approved by the executive board. The WP is struggling with access to approvals and data, because of the delay related to including AAU into the FEMaLe Consortium.

We are in the process of developing an analysis plan for moving forward in how to run the analysis instead of teared sections moving from the UK biobank data, that PrecisionLife analysis, to DBDS data that we have access to.

Overall Impact – KPI/measure

What were the KPIs?

1. To get Aalborg University approved as FEMaLe beneficiary to establish rhythm and flow in WP4.
2. To employ 3 dedicated staff.

Were the targets met?

We have partially reached the intended targets. This means that we will continue with the tasks that did not reach the intended targets in the WP4 Impact Case in Q1+Q2 2022 and additionally set new targets for 2022 Q1 and Q2.

WP5

In more detail

The Lucy app has been released and translated into English, Danish and Swedish. The software architecture behind the app has been restructured.

Further, we have been developing the Lucy Questionnaire to be utilized in the longitudinal study. The method is to make a one year perspective. The collected data will be analyzed using artificial intelligence.

We hope to find new patterns, clusters and connections that could lead to a better and faster diagnosis or to pinpoint women who need to get checked by a doctor.

Overall Impact – KPI/measure

What were the KPIs?

1. To generate a recruitment plan per target country to attract Lucy App users.
2. To validate and translate the content of the Lucy App into Danish and Swedish.
3. To validate the baseline questionnaire.

Were the targets met?

We have partially reached the intended targets. This means that we will continue with the tasks that did not reach the intended targets in the WP5 Impact Case in Q1+Q2 2022 and additionally set new targets for 2022 Q1 and Q2.

WP6 + WP7

In more detail

In WP6 we have started to collect video data and gained access to SurgAR sample segmentation tools. We are currently waiting for real patients' data of laparoscopic videos. We started collecting data last month. Multiple specialists are going through an annotation learning process. We arranged a meeting with local GDPR experts to help with patients' video/data sharing. We are trying to adopt a semi-supervised image segmentation algorithm from other projects, which will make the segmentation in our project much easier and faster.

In WP7 we have been collecting videos with metadata. We started the annotation and training for surgeon labellers. We have trained five labellers (Hungarian and French surgeons) so far. Semmelweis Hospital finally started data collection, and Clermont-Ferrand will continue. In terms of obtaining ethical approval, Aarhus University Hospital still awaits permission. As a consequence, we have re-allocated funding to SurgAR for deploying an approved data collection process, securing that we meet our targets. Further, we hope to get access to more retrospective data in other centers, and we are in dialogue with potential collaborators in Brazil, Italy, and France.

Overall Impact – KPI/measure

What were the KPIs?

1. To define tasks needed to subcontract, clarify budget, and get administration approval.
2. To recruit 10 annotators.
3. To reach 1 new scientific collaborator.
4. To reach legal and ethical approvals.
5. To reach 2 subcontracts
6. To establish an event with French policy makers to promote FemTech and Endometriosis.

Were the targets met?

We have partially reached the intended targets. This means that we will continue with the tasks that did not reach the intended targets in the WP6-WP7 Impact Case in Q1+Q2 2022 and additionally set new targets for 2022 Q1 and Q2.

WP8

In more detail

We have finished three out of ten mindfulness modules for MY-ENDO. Yoga exercises are transcribed for session one in Danish and will be translated into English. A master student will feasibility test the first four sessions of the mindfulness program. The whole project and the MY-ENDO results have been presented at the Danish Endometriosis Patients Associations' Yearly Meeting, and we find that this has implications for both the patient organization and the patients with endometriosis.

The three sessions are currently at a mindfulness expertise review. Some corrections are needed which are already on track. There will be a meeting with the University of Oxford to discuss the translation into English. The platform Vimeo will be used to host the videos.

We have designed the MY-ENDO program software that will be used for mindfulness digitalisation. It is designed as a Wordpress webpage with a Learndash plugin included.

Overall Impact – KPI/measure

What were the KPIs?

1. To test the pilot program modules.
2. To translate the video into English and Hungarian.
3. To validate and translate the My Endo program.
4. To generate a recruitment plan for the My Endo program.
5. To establish contact with Endometriosis Units/Clinics and Patient Associations.
6. To investigate the capacity of the recruitment of the RCT and how to increase it.

Were the targets met?

We have partially reached the intended targets. This means that we will continue with the tasks that did not reach the intended targets in the WP8 Impact Case in Q1+Q2 2022 and additionally set new targets for 2022 Q1 and Q2. WP8 agreed to start the pilot program modules in February 2022.

WP9

In more detail

We have utilized the social media accounts for the project to communicate about FE-MaLe and to disseminate its major results. The first animated explainer video was also finalized and published on social media platforms before New Year's. Great effort of multiple partners providing feedback and commenting on the video.

Furthermore, we have started working on the project's main website to replace the temporary version, which will gather all the communications effort regarding the project.

We participated actively in the Danish Endometriosis Patients' Association's Annual Meeting 1 October 2021 and told the story about the FEMaLe project, shared initial results about the MY-ENDO program and recruited patients with endometriosis as participants for the upcoming Awareness Month Campaign (March 2022).

In the WP9 impact case workshop, we agreed upon the action to develop the FEMaLe's website and a communication plan and to establish workshops to identify 2 relevant events.

Overall Impact – KPI/measure

What were the KPIs?

1. To develop the FEMaLe's website and a communication plan.
2. To establish workshops to identify 2 relevant events.

Were the targets met?

We have partially reached the intended targets. This means that we will continue with the tasks that did not reach the intended targets in the WP9 Impact Case in Q1+Q2 2022 and additionally set new targets for 2022 Q1 and Q2.

WP10

In more detail

We held Executive Board meetings in February, March, April, May, August, October and December, and we conducted Work Package Leader meetings in June, September and November.

We have established fixed rhythms, which help the FEMaLers to collaborate across the 10 work packages. Aarhus University hosted the very first physical, international FE-MaLe interactions after COVID-19 lockdowns together with EQUIP and CORRELATE from Norway at Aarhus University and ARoS Art Museum over a two full-day seminar, which was wonderful and productive. We identified needs and prioritized them to guide the development and improvement of the Correlate FEMaLe platform.

Overall Impact – KPI/measure

What were the KPIs?

1. To demonstrate the Correlate prototype platform to the FEMaLe consortium.
2. To conduct a needs assessment about usage of Correlate in the FEMaLe Project.
3. To create Correlate training sessions/workshops for the FEMaLe partners.
4. To establish a Correlate support team for the FEMaLe partners.
5. To pulse check FEMaLe stakeholders to monitor level of satisfaction.
6. To establish 5 Correlate seminar.
7. To identify Correlate folder structure.

Were the targets met?

We have partially reached the intended targets. This means that we will continue with the tasks that did not reach the intended targets in the WP10 Impact Case in Q1+Q2 2022 and additionally set new targets for 2022 Q1 and Q2.

A FEW MORE WORDS

Thank you very much for 2021, 2022 is already shaping up to be even better on all possible metrics with our first consortium-wide meeting in March it will be a true privilege to meet you all in person.

In the meantime and if you haven't done so already, please follow FEMaLe on social media and interact with us and the united endometriosis community!

*click the icons to start to
engage already today!*

